

Forschungsmodul

Numerical Modeling and Implementation of Non-Isothermal Two-Phase, Three-Component Flow for Evaporation and Gas Exchange in DuMu^x

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Abstract

Rising temperatures driven by climate change pose a significant threat to the preservation of prehistoric sites, such as the Lascaux cave, where fluctuations in temperature and humidity create a favorable microclimate for microbial and fungal growth, which directly endanger ancient wall paintings.

This work presents the development and implementation of a non-isothermal, two-phase, three-component numerical model designed to simulate the coupled transport of water, air, and CO_2 in the porous soil and rock layers above such systems. The mathematical formulation is based on Darcy-scale component balance equations coupled with a single energy conservation equation under the assumption of local thermal equilibrium. Thermodynamic closure is achieved through capillary pressure relations, Henry's law, Raoult's law, and ideal-gas assumptions. The model is implemented in the open-source simulation framework DuMu^x as a custom formulation with atmospheric coupling through flux-based Neumann boundary conditions.

Particular emphasis is placed on the soil-atmosphere interface, where a boundary condition system derived from the Penman-Monteith framework and the Bowen ratio governs the surface energy balance. Within this framework, evapotranspiration is identified as the critical link between mass and energy balances, acting as a dominant cooling mechanism.

To evaluate the implementation, a sandy soil column is subjected to meteorological forcing data to compare different temporal interpolation strategies. The results demonstrate that a synthetic diurnal cycle is essential to capture realistic day-night dynamics, such as midday evapotranspiration peaks and nocturnal radiative cooling. Furthermore, simulations show that sufficient domain depth is required to provide a capillary buffer, preventing numerical failure during intense evaporative demand.

This framework establishes a robust and physically consistent basis for future studies of coupled soil-atmosphere-cave systems and the integration of active CO_2 transport processes essential for the preservation of cultural heritage.

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1 Introduction

Rising temperatures are altering environmental systems on a global scale. In cave environments, these changes pose a particular challenge for conservation efforts, as even slight changes in temperature or humidity can trigger the metabolic activity of microorganisms, such as bacteria and fungi, which pose a severe threat to the preservation of prehistoric wall paintings. The Lascaux cave in southern France illustrates the importance of understanding how these increasing temperatures influence the distribution of subsurface CO₂, air and water vapor. Early documentation of the Lascaux cave provided initial observations on microclimate variability and raised critical conservation concerns shortly after its discovery in 1940 [22].

Subsequent research has expanded the understanding of these dynamics through long-term monitoring and numerical modeling. Malaurent et al. [23] evaluated the Lascaux microclimate, seasonal signals, and human-induced perturbations to model environmental parameters. Furthermore, Peyraube et al. [28] analyzed and modeled ventilation patterns and CO₂ fluctuations, concluding that temperature, water flow, and atmospheric pressure are the main drivers of CO₂ levels. Recent work by Lacanette et al. [20, 21] represents the current state-of-practice in numerical modeling of heat and mass transfer within the Lascaux rock-air system, specifically addressing management scenarios and wall exchanges.

To complement this cave-centered modeling, this work aims to develop a sub-system that models the heat and mass transfer in the soil and rock above the cave and its exchange with the atmosphere. This approach is informed by a DuMu^x-based study on coupled heat and moisture transport with meteorological forcing by Nissler et al. [27], particularly regarding the treatment of atmosphere-subsurface coupling via surface fluxes. At the soil-atmosphere interface, evaporation and heat exchange are commonly represented by surface energy balance concepts and aerodynamic formulations. Allen et al. [2] formalized these processes in the Penman-Monteith framework, combining an energy balance with mass transfer and resistances to estimate evapotranspiration from meteorological data. Monteith and Unsworth [24] provide a comprehensive treatment of the environmental physics underlying these balances. Trouffleau et al. [33] parameterized sensible heat flux and resistances over heterogeneous land surfaces, while Xu et al. [37, 36] highlighted the role of surface vapor pressure gradients when investigating soil evaporation under coupled heat-vapor diffusion and capillarity. Motivated by these findings, this work couples component mass balances with an energy balance and

focuses on the role of evaporation at the soil-atmosphere interface.

The description of multiphase, multicomponent transport in the subsurface is based on Darcy-scale mass and momentum balances with relative permeabilities, derived by Bear [6]. Heat transport is synthesized through convection and buoyancy within the porous media [25], utilizing specific material constants for the necessary thermodynamic closure relations [31].

In general, this work connects conservation-motivated questions in cave environments with coupled mass and energy transport in porous media and across the soil-atmosphere interface. We investigate the energy and mass flux response to increasing temperature, using a system that includes air and CO₂ to ensure physical consistency for future transport studies of coupled soil-atmosphere systems above caves.

This is approached by developing a non-isothermal two-phase, three-component flow model with energy transport in porous media and implementing it in the open-source C++ simulation framework DuMu^x [14, 18]. In the present scope, the free-flow atmosphere and the cave air space are not modeled as separate fluid domains. Instead, atmospheric influence is incorporated through boundary conditions at the top boundary, while explicit coupling to a cave domain is deferred to future work. The resulting model is therefore a simplified first-step framework that can later be extended to include free-flow air regions and detailed cave geometries, while already providing a physically consistent basis for quantifying energy and mass transfer from the atmosphere through the soil and rock towards a cave system. Ultimately, this framework can be used to extend existing models of cave systems and to improve our understanding of how to preserve and protect prehistoric cave paintings from external environmental changes.

The structure of this work is organized as follows. Chapter 2 provides the theory of foundational physics, porous media flow, phase behavior, and coupled heat and mass transfer processes that underlie the model. Chapter 3 formulates the governing equations, constitutive relations, and boundary conditions for the non-isothermal two-phase, three-component system. In Chapter 4 the numerical implementation details are presented, including the software considerations within the DuMu^x framework. Chapter 5 presents simulation results and analyzes the influence of temperature changes on surface energy partitioning and water mass fluxes. Finally, Chapter 6 summarizes the main findings, discusses the limitations of the current approach, and suggests directions for future research.

2 Physical Concepts

This chapter introduces the fundamental physical concepts underlying the coupled mass and energy transport processes. Starting from general two-phase flow properties in porous media, we introduce the concepts of capillarity and phase interactions, what constitutes a multi-component system, the key concepts of thermal effects and evaporation, as well as specific theory of subsurface caves. The goal is to provide a qualitative physical background for the mathematical formulations derived in Chapter 3.

2.1 Multiphase Flow in Porous Media

The physics of flow in soils or rocks is commonly described by modeling such materials as porous media [13]. A porous medium consists of a solid matrix and an interconnected void space. The key properties that define a porous medium are porosity and permeability. The porosity ϕ of a porous medium is a measure of the void spaces of the material. It is the fraction of the volume of void spaces over the total volume of the material which includes both solid and void components. Permeability \mathbf{K} represents the ability of the medium to transmit fluids. It depends on the porosity as well as the shapes of the pores and their connectedness. High porosity means that the medium can store a lot of fluid and high permeability means that the fluid can move easily through the medium.

In a two-phase flow scenario, two immiscible fluids (mixture does not form a solution) coexist in the pore space [17]. The fluid that coats the pore walls is considered the wetting phase ($\alpha = w$) and the fluid that occupies the central pore regions is considered the non-wetting phase ($\alpha = n$), see Figure 2.1. In our case, the wetting phase is a liquid phase, and the non-wetting phase is a gas phase. Each phase α occupies a certain fraction of the pore volume, denoted by the saturation S_α . For two phases, saturation is defined so that $S_w + S_n = 1$. The saturation of one phase rarely reaches 0 or 1 because instead of a phase completely vanishing, residual saturations remain in the form of e.g. trapped air bubbles or bound water that cannot be drained.

At the continuum scale, fluid flow velocities are described by Darcy's law, which states that the volumetric flux is proportional to the pressure drop and the permeability of the medium [6]. In the presence of multiple phases, the second fluid impedes the flow. This is quantified by the relative permeability $k_{r\alpha}(S_\alpha)$, which increases with the saturation

Figure 2.1: Schematic porous medium with wetting and non-wetting fluids.

and decreases as the phase becomes more disconnected. These concepts ensure the realistic water and gas movement in our model. Water will tend to flow in wetter zones and can become immobile if only disconnected patches remain, whereas gas can move through air-filled pore channels but may be blocked in water-saturated zones.

2.2 Capillarity and Phase Interaction

Interfaces between two phases cause the rise of capillary forces. They originate from the fluid-fluid interfacial tension and the wetting characteristics of the solid [6]. At a curved liquid-gas interface a difference in pressures forms. The pressure in the non-wetting phase p_n is higher than the pressure in the wetting phase p_w by an amount denoted by the capillary pressure $p_c = p_n - p_w$. The capillary pressure thus pulls the wetting fluid into narrow pores, where the smaller the pore, the stronger the capillary pressure and the greater the curvature of the interface. This leads to the physical effect of high capillary suction in dry soils (low S_w) leading to the water being held tightly in small pores and low capillary suction in wet soils (high S_w) leading to water being released easily. Typical constitutive relations describing this behavior through relating capillary pressures and saturations as well as relative permeability functions were introduced by van Genuchten [34] and Brooks-Corey [12]. They ensure the closure of the two-phase system.

The contact angles and pore geometry influence a phenomenon called hysteresis, which describes that drying and wetting paths follow different curves [17].

Overall, capillarity and phase interactions determine how water is retained and released from the soil and how the presence of one fluid affects the other.

2.3 Multi-Component Gas-Liquid System

Our system consists of three components, namely water H_2O , carbon dioxide CO_2 , and a pseudo-component Air that represents the mixture of nitrogen, oxygen, and argon. These three components are distributed in the two previously introduced phases. H_2O exists mainly as a liquid but also as vapor in the gas phase, CO_2 exists as a free gas in the pore space or as a dissolved gas in the liquid phase, and Air makes up the bulk of the gas phase but can also have a small amount dissolved in water.

In a gas mixture, each component contributes to the total pressure according to Dalton's law [10]. The gas phase pressure p_n is the sum of the partial pressures $p_n = p_n^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + p_n^{\text{CO}_2} + p_n^{\text{Air}}$. These partial pressures can also be used to define the composition of the gas in the form of mole fractions of the components $x_n^k = p_n^k/p_n$. We assume ideal gas behavior, which allows relating pressure, temperature, and gas density. This assumption is reasonable under typical soil-atmosphere conditions.

The partition of components between the two phases is governed by thermodynamic equilibrium relations. Henry's law applies for components that are present in trace amounts in the liquid, such as the sparingly soluble gases CO_2 and Air [11]. It states that at equilibrium, the concentration in the liquid is proportional to its partial pressure in the gas. The proportionality coefficient, called Henry's coefficient, indicates how well the component dissolves in the liquid and is temperature dependent [31]. CO_2 is moderately soluble in water, whereas the bulk Air components are much less soluble and have higher Henry's coefficients. Gases generally become less soluble at higher temperatures, which is physically important as the warming of water can result in the release of dissolved CO_2 as gas bubbles. For the solvent, in our case water, the equilibrium between the liquid and the gas phase is described by Raoult's law [29]. It describes how the vapor pressure is related to the liquid mole fraction through the saturation vapor pressure of water at a certain temperature. The saturation vapor pressure increases exponentially with temperature. If the actual vapor pressure is below the saturation vapor pressure, evaporation can occur until the vapor reaches its equilibrium pressure. If it exceeds the saturation vapor pressure, condensation will occur to remove excess vapor.

We assume that phase changes occur instantaneously, so that local equilibrium is maintained at the pore scale. Then, Henry and Raoult's law can be used to relate the phase composition to the local pressure and temperature, and thus form the thermodynamic closure needed to solve for the composition of each phase, as will be detailed in Chapter 3. Overall, the model can thus capture key phenomena such as water evaporating into the air phase when it is dry, or CO_2 being released from the water, while conserving the mass of every component.

2.4 Energy and Heat Transport

In addition to mass transport, our model also accounts for the transport of heat. We assume the porous medium to be in a local thermal equilibrium, which means that the liquid and gas phases and the solid matrix share a common temperature locally, because of efficient heat exchange at the pore scale. Under this assumption, we can write a single energy conservation equation for the combined system rather than separate ones for each phase. Local thermal equilibrium is a valid assumption at the Darcy scale due to the large interfacial area between phases and the rapid heat exchange relative to advective transport [25].

The main transport mechanisms for heat are conduction and advection [35]. Conduction occurs as a result of temperature gradients. In a porous medium, heat is conducted through both the solid material and the fluid in the pores. The effective thermal conductivity λ_{pm} for the combined medium depends on properties such as the saturation of both the solid and fluids. A wet soil will generally conduct heat more than a dry soil because the thermal conductivity of water is significantly higher than that of air. Advection is the transport of heat by the bulk movement of fluids. If a fluid flows from one location to another, it carries its internal energy with it and can thus significantly influence the temperature distribution.

Another important feature of a two-phase system with phase changes is the latent heat [2]. It represents the heat required to convert a liquid into a vapor or vapor into liquid without change of temperature, and thus occurs when water evaporates or condenses. When water evaporates, it requires absorbing a certain amount of energy, namely the latent heat of vaporization λ_{ET} . This causes a cooling effect in the surrounding material. However, when vapor condenses to a liquid, the latent heat is released as thermal energy into the surroundings. To model these processes, we include an energy conservation equation that accounts for the internal energy of each phase and the solid, and the pressure forces in terms of enthalpy transport. Each phase has a specific enthalpy that includes sensible and latent heat and thus naturally includes the effects of phase changes. The energy equation thus captures how heat conduction, fluid flow, and phase changes interact. Including the energy equation in our model then allows us to realistically model physical feedback, such as a warmer soil having a higher vapor pressure of water, which promotes evaporation and thus cooling of the soil, and a lower CO_2 solubility, which promotes the release of CO_2 , and gas expansion redistributing heat.

2.5 Soil-Atmosphere Interaction and Evaporation

One of the physical processes contributing to the surface energy balance that governs the mass and energy fluxes between the land surface and the atmosphere is net radiation R_{net} [16]. It is the primary driver of surface heating and includes absorbed shortwave solar radiation and longwave thermal radiation, minus outgoing components. Another process is the ground heat flux G that represents the conductive heat flow from the surface into the soil. The sensible heat flux H_{sens} represents the convective heat transfer from the surface to the atmosphere. Evaporation from the soil surface is a key process in soil-atmosphere exchange [7]. This phase change of water from liquid to vapor is described by the latent heat flux H_{ET} . It represents the energy consumed by evaporation without a change in temperature and is directly tied to the mass flux of water vapor leaving the surface into the atmosphere. Evapotranspiration ET refers to the water mass flux and includes both soil evaporation and plant transpiration. In terms of energy balance, ET contributes to the latent heat flux H_{ET} which, together with the heat flux due to precipitation, constitutes the water heat flux $H_{\text{waterflux}}$. The total soil-atmosphere interaction is then described by the way these fluxes are balanced.

Evaporation mechanisms at different soil moisture states can be conceptualized in two regimes. In a moisture-rich condition, evaporation is predominantly controlled by energy available for phase change and atmospheric demand, which can be quantified through Penman-Monteith formulations [2, 24]. As surface moisture is depleted, the limiting factor becomes the ability of the soil to supply liquid water to the surface, which is controlled by the hydraulic properties of the soil and the moisture gradients [3]. The Penman-Monteith equation merges the surface energy balance with a mass transfer formulation based on aerodynamic and surface resistances to estimate evapotranspiration rates from meteorological data.

In soil models without an explicit atmospheric boundary layer, the evaporation boundary condition is often expressed as a vapor pressure or relative humidity gradient between pore-air at the surface and an external atmospheric reference height, combined with aerodynamic resistance and soil surface conductance. This formulation captures first-order evaporative flux behavior in a computationally efficient way while maintaining a physical basis in surface energy balance theory [2]. An applied example of implementing this interface-balance approach in DuMu^x for non-isothermal subsurface problems is given by Nissler et al. [27].

2.6 Application Context: Subsurface CO₂ Transport

CO₂ exchanged between the subsurface, soil, and cave atmospheres plays a critical role in both ecosystem carbon dynamics and the conservation of subterranean environments. In many karst systems, soil respiration associated with microbial decay of

organic matter and plant root activity is the dominant source of CO_2 produced above caves. This gas can diffuse or advect through the soil profile and rock matrix, eventually entering cave passages either as a free gas or bound in solution in water seepages. Inside caves, CO_2 may also accumulate from human presence or other biological or geochemical processes [28, 11].

The climate within a cave, which encompasses air temperature, humidity, and gas concentrations, is inherently linked to exchanges with the outside atmosphere and the surrounding vadose zone. Although caves often exhibit relatively stable microclimates due to buffering by the enclosing rock mass and limited direct exposure to external fluctuations, they are not closed systems. Slow exchanges of heat, moisture, and gases through fractures, conduits, and porous rock connect cave internal conditions to surface ones. This coupling influences the thermal and chemical environment of the cave and has implications for the preservation of cultural heritage [23, 8, 21].

CO_2 transport into and within the subsurface can occur via molecular diffusion, where concentration gradients drive flux, or via advective flow, driven by pressure gradients, temperature differences, and ventilation patterns. Variations in outside atmospheric conditions, such as seasonal temperature cycles or barometric changes can influence these driving forces and thus the rate and direction of CO_2 exchange. Ventilation patterns within the cave network, controlled by geometry, external winds, and density contrasts, also significantly influence the spatial and temporal distribution of CO_2 [19, 30, 11].

The solubility of CO_2 in water is temperature dependent. As temperature increases, CO_2 becomes less soluble, leading to exsolution of gas from water and potentially increasing partial pressure in the gas phase. This effect, coupled with thermal stratification of air masses and changing gas exchange rates at the cave-soil-atmosphere interfaces, underscores the importance of coupled thermal and mass transport processes in controlling subsurface CO_2 dynamics [28].

Within the context of this work, providing a model that includes CO_2 and water vapor alongside heat fluxes establishes a robust foundation for modeling the exchange processes that influence cave microclimates. The soil-rock layer above a cave acts as a buffer, mediating the transfer of energy and mass between the surface and subterranean cavity. Capturing these coupled processes is thus a prerequisite for robustly predicting how cave gas concentrations respond to external environmental forces and internal sources [9].

While CO_2 is included as a component in the model to facilitate these future applications, the present analysis focuses on the boundary layer processes that drive the overall system.

3 Mathematical Modeling

This chapter presents the mathematical model used to simulate coupled mass and energy transport processes in a porous medium.

Starting from physical principles and empirical relations, we derive governing equations and boundary conditions consistent with a two-phase, three-component system.

Relevant symbols and their physical meanings and units are compiled in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Nomenclature of core variables used in mathematical model.

Symbol	Description	Unit
α	Fluid phase	—
w	Wetting (liquid) phase	—
n	Non-wetting (gas) phase	—
κ	Chemical component	—
ϕ	Porosity of the porous medium	—
$\rho_{\alpha}^{\text{mol}}$	Molar density of phase α	mol/m ³
x_{α}^{κ}	Mole fraction of component κ in phase α	—
S_{α}	Saturation of phase α	—
p_{α}	Pressure in phase α	Pa
T	Temperature	K
H_{α}^{κ}	Henry coefficient of component κ in phase α	Pa·m ³ /mol
$p_{\text{sat}}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	Saturation vapor pressure of water	Pa
G	Soil heat flux	J/m ² ·s
R_{net}	Net radiation	J/m ² ·s
H_{sens}	Sensible heat flux	J/m ² ·s
$H_{\text{waterflux}}$	Water enthalpy flux	J/m ² ·s
H_{ET}	Latent heat flux	J/m ² ·s
c_p	Specific heat capacity of air	J/kg·K
r_a	Aerodynamic resistance	s/m
ET	Evapotranspiration rate	mol/m ² ·s
P	Precipitation rate	mol/m ² ·s
γ	Psychrometric constant	Pa/K
ε	Ratio of molecular weights (vapor/dry air), 0.622	—
λ	Latent heat of vaporization	J/kg
e	Vapor pressure	Pa
j^{κ}	Flux of component κ	mol/m ² ·s

3.1 Balance Equations

We consider a two-phase, three-component system, consisting of two compressible and partially miscible fluid phases, denoted by $\alpha \in \{w, n\}$, where w represents the wetting (liquid) phase and n the non-wetting (gas) phase. Solid phases are not explicitly modeled in this work. The chemical components present in the fluid phases are denoted by $\kappa \in \{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{CO}_2, \text{Air}\}$. The component "Air" is treated as a single pseudo-component representing a mixture of 78.166% nitrogen (N_2), 20.9% oxygen (O_2), and 0.934% argon (Ar). Interactions between components and phases include phase change as well as dissolution and precipitation reactions. In the present scope, the mole balance for CO_2 is computed to ensure model completeness, though its concentration is initialized and maintained at zero in the simulations in Chapter 5.

The model described in the following chapters follows the convention of the two-phase multi-component (2pnc) framework of DuMu^x as documented in dumux.org.

Momentum Conservation The momentum transfer in each fluid phase is governed by Darcy's law, which models flow in porous media under low Reynolds number conditions. It describes the advective flux resulting from both pressure gradients and gravitational forces. For single-phase flow, the velocity v is given by:

$$v = -\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu}(\nabla p - \rho \mathbf{g}), \quad (3.1)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the absolute permeability tensor of the porous medium, μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid, p is the pressure, ρ is the fluid density, and \mathbf{g} is the gravitational acceleration vector.

For multiple phases, the velocity of phase α is modified to account for relative permeability effects due to the presence of other phases. The resulting expression is as follows:

$$v_\alpha = -\frac{k_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha} \mathbf{K}(\nabla p_\alpha - \rho_\alpha \mathbf{g}), \quad (3.2)$$

where $k_{r\alpha}$ is the relative permeability and μ_α , p_α , and ρ_α are the viscosity, pressure, and density of phase α , respectively.

These phase velocities are substituted into the mole conservation equations to describe component transport, resulting in a fully coupled system of equations.

Mole Conservation In order to accurately simulate fluid flow, heat transfer and chemical processes in porous media we compute component balance equations. Since our simulation focuses on mole fractions, we use a general mole conservation equation for

each component κ :

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\sum_{\alpha} \phi \rho_{\alpha}^{\text{mol}} x_{\alpha}^{\kappa} S_{\alpha} \right) + \sum_{\alpha} \nabla \cdot \{ \rho_{\alpha}^{\text{mol}} x_{\alpha}^{\kappa} v_{\alpha} \} - \sum_{\alpha} \nabla \cdot \{ \mathbf{D}_{\alpha, \text{pm}}^{\kappa} \rho_{\alpha}^{\text{mol}} \nabla x_{\alpha}^{\kappa} \} - \sum_{\alpha} q_{\alpha}^{\kappa} = 0, \quad (3.3)$$

$$\alpha \in \{n, w\}, \quad \kappa \in \{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{CO}_2, \text{Air}\},$$

where the first term is a storage term, the second an advective term, the third a diffusive term, and the last a source/sink term. Here ϕ is the porosity of the porous medium, S_{α} represents the saturation of phase α , $\rho_{\alpha}^{\text{mol}}$ is the mole density of phase α , x_{α}^{κ} is the mole fraction of component κ in phase α , v_{α} is the velocity of phase α , $\mathbf{D}_{\alpha, \text{pm}}^{\kappa}$ is the effective diffusivity of component κ in phase α , and q_{α}^{κ} is a source or sink term.

Substituting Darcy's law (3.2) into these component balance equations yields one full mole transport equation for each component:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\sum_{\alpha} \phi \rho_{\alpha}^{\text{mol}} x_{\alpha}^{\kappa} S_{\alpha} \right) - \sum_{\alpha} \nabla \cdot \left\{ \rho_{\alpha}^{\text{mol}} x_{\alpha}^{\kappa} \frac{k_{r\alpha}}{\mu_{\alpha}} \mathbf{K} (\nabla p_{\alpha} - \rho_{\alpha}^{\text{mol}} \mathbf{g}) \right\} - \sum_{\alpha} \nabla \cdot \{ \mathbf{D}_{\alpha, \text{pm}}^{\kappa} \rho_{\alpha}^{\text{mol}} \nabla x_{\alpha}^{\kappa} \} - \sum_{\alpha} q_{\alpha}^{\kappa} = 0, \quad (3.4)$$

This equation forms the basis for tracking the spatial and temporal evolution of each component in the system.

Energy Conservation To model a non-isothermal simulation we introduce an additional balance equation for the energy. It models convective and conductive processes while assuming local thermal equilibrium. The energy conservation equation is given by:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\sum_{\alpha} \phi \rho_{\alpha}^{\text{mol}} S_{\alpha} (u_{\alpha} - \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{x}) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} ((1 - \phi) \rho_s^{\text{mol}} c_s T) - \sum_{\alpha} \nabla \cdot \left\{ \rho_{\alpha}^{\text{mol}} (h_{\alpha} - \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{x}) \frac{k_{r\alpha}}{\mu_{\alpha}} \mathbf{K} (\nabla p_{\alpha} - \rho_{\alpha}^{\text{mol}} \mathbf{g}) \right\} - \nabla \cdot (\lambda_{\text{pm}} \nabla T) - q^h = 0, \quad (3.5)$$

where u_{α} is the specific internal energy of phase α , \mathbf{x} is the position in space, ρ_s^{mol} is the mole density of the solid phase, c_s is the heat capacity of the solid phase, T is the temperature, h_{α} is the specific enthalpy of phase α , λ_{pm} is the effective heat conductivity in the porous medium, and q^h is a source or sink term.

Together with the mole conservation, this energy conservation equation provides a complete description of component transport in a non-isothermal multiphase system. This coupling enables the simulation of fully coupled heat and mole transport in realistic subsurface environments.

3.2 Primary Variables and Thermodynamic Closure

In multiphase compositional transport models, the selection of primary variables and thermodynamic closure relations is critical to accurately modeling phase behavior and component transport.

Gibbs phase rule determines the number of independent thermodynamic constraints (degrees of freedom) in a system at a local thermodynamic equilibrium. It is given by:

$$\#\text{DOF} = n_{\text{components}} - n_{\text{phases}} + 2. \quad (3.6)$$

For a non-isothermal two-phase three-component system, we get:

$$\#\text{DOF} = 3 - 2 + 2 = 3. \quad (3.7)$$

This means that three intensive variables are sufficient to describe a system at a local equilibrium. However, since we model transport processes, which are non-equilibrium and spatially distributed, we require a fourth primary variable to solve the governing conservation equations.

Primary Variable Selection We adopt the two-phase formulation `p1s0`, which defines the pressure of the second phase and the saturation of the first phase as primary variables. In our case, this corresponds to the pressure of the non-wetting (gas) phase p_n and the saturation of the wetting (liquid) phase S_w .

To account for compositional and thermal effects, we include the mole fraction of CO_2 in the liquid phase $x_w^{\text{CO}_2}$ and the temperature T . Thus, our system uses the following four primary variables:

$$\{p_n, S_w, x_w^{\text{CO}_2}, T\}. \quad (3.8)$$

Derivation of Secondary Variables The remaining unknowns in the multiphase-flow Equation (3.4), which must be derived from the primary variables, are the following:

$$\{p_w, S_n, x_n^{\text{CO}_2}, x_n^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}, x_w^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}, x_n^{\text{Air}}, x_w^{\text{Air}}\}. \quad (3.9)$$

These secondary variables are obtained through thermodynamic and constitutive closure relations as shown in the following.

The capillary pressure is a function of the saturation of the liquid phase $p_c = f(S_w)$ and is related to the phase pressures via:

$$p_c = p_n - p_w \Rightarrow p_w = p_n - f(S_w), \quad (3.10)$$

which allows us to compute the pressure of the liquid phase.

The saturation constraint $\sum_{\alpha} S_{\alpha} = 1$ gives an equation for the saturation of the gas phase:

$$S_n = 1 - S_w. \quad (3.11)$$

Assuming ideal gas behavior, Dalton's law for the partial pressures of a mixture of gases gives:

$$p_n = \sum_{\kappa} p_n^{\kappa}, \quad (3.12)$$

where p_n^{κ} is the partial pressure exerted by component κ on the gas mixture. The mole fraction in the gas phase is:

$$x_n^{\kappa} = \frac{p_n^{\kappa}}{p_n}. \quad (3.13)$$

The composition of each phase can be related to the partial pressure of the liquid phase using Henry's law:

$$p_n^{\kappa} = x_{\alpha}^{\kappa} \cdot H_{\alpha}^{\kappa}(T), \quad (3.14)$$

where H_{α}^{κ} is the temperature dependent Henry coefficient of the component κ in the phase α .

Inserting Equation (3.14) into Equation (3.13) results in:

$$x_n^{\kappa} = \frac{x_{\alpha}^{\kappa} \cdot H_{\alpha}^{\kappa}(T)}{p_n}. \quad (3.15)$$

This allows for a direct computation of the CO₂ mole fraction in the gas phase:

$$x_n^{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{x_w^{\text{CO}_2} \cdot H_w^{\text{CO}_2}(T)}{p_n}. \quad (3.16)$$

Solving for Remaining Mole Fractions The remaining four mole fractions $x_n^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $x_w^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, x_n^{Air} , x_w^{Air} can be calculated using the following relations.

Raoult's law for an ideal solution at a local thermal equilibrium for the H₂O component states:

$$p_n^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = x_w^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \cdot p_{\text{sat}}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(T), \quad (3.17)$$

where $p_{\text{sat}}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the temperature dependent saturation vapor pressure of pure water.

1. Using Raoult's and Dalton's law for H₂O in the liquid phase gives:

$$x_w^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \frac{x_n^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} p_n}{p_{\text{sat}}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(T)} \quad (3.18)$$

2. Using Henry's and Dalton's law for Air in the liquid phase gives:

$$x_n^{\text{Air}} = \frac{x_w^{\text{Air}} H_w^{\text{Air}}}{p_n} \quad (3.19)$$

3. Using the mole fraction closure of the liquid phase gives:

$$\sum_{\kappa} x_w^{\kappa} = 1 \quad \Rightarrow \quad x_w^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + x_w^{\text{Air}} = 1 - x_w^{\text{CO}_2} \quad (3.20)$$

4. Using the mole fraction closure of the gas phase gives:

$$\sum_{\kappa} x_n^{\kappa} = 1 \quad \Rightarrow \quad x_n^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + x_n^{\text{Air}} = 1 - x_n^{\text{CO}_2} \quad (3.21)$$

These four constraints form a linear system which can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{p_n}{p_{\text{sat}}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(T)} & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -\frac{H_w^{\text{Air}}(T)}{p_n} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_n^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \\ x_w^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \\ x_n^{\text{Air}} \\ x_w^{\text{Air}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 - x_w^{\text{CO}_2} \\ 1 - x_n^{\text{CO}_2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.22)$$

Solving this system yields the mole fractions of the remaining components in both the gas and liquid phase, completing the set of secondary variables. The matrix is nonsingular under physical conditions and thus gives a unique solution.

3.3 Boundary Conditions

In this section, we define the boundary conditions used in the model and derive expressions for surface heat and mole fluxes relevant to evapotranspiration. These are implemented as Neumann boundary conditions in DuMu^x.

Neumann zero boundary conditions are imposed on all domain boundaries except the top boundary. These boundary conditions specify that the normal derivative of the field variables is zero at the boundary:

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = 0, \quad (3.23)$$

where v denotes a generic dependent variable (e.g., pressure, mole fraction, or temperature), and \mathbf{n} is the outward-pointing normal vector at the boundary.

Physically, this condition implies that there is no flux across the boundary of the variable v . In the context of momentum, mole, or energy transport, this corresponds to no inflow or outflow across the bottom, left, and right boundaries of the domain.

As a result, the domain behaves like an isolated box on these three sides. Interactions with the surroundings are restricted solely to the top boundary, which represents the ground surface.

This assumption is justified by our modeling objective of focusing on vertical transport phenomena such as evaporation, condensation, and gas exchange with the atmosphere.

Lateral and bottom fluxes are assumed to be negligible in comparison having chosen a sufficiently large domain.

The Neumann boundary conditions used at the top boundary are derived in the following section.

The ground-atmosphere interface models two physical processes, namely heat exchange and mole exchange. These fluxes are split into these categories in accordance with the governing conservation laws. The heat balance is applied in the energy conservation equation, while the mole balance contributes to mass conservation of each component.

3.3.1 Energy Flux Boundary Condition

We formulate the surface energy balance at the top boundary following the Penman-Monteith framework of Allen et al. [2] and the DuMu^x-oriented implementation strategy represented by Nissler et al. [27], but we derive the boundary flux expressions consistently with the present two-phase, three component model. The surface energy balance of our system reads as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Soil heat flux} &= \text{Net radiation} & - \text{Sensible heat flux} & + \text{Water flux}, & (3.24) \\ \Leftrightarrow G &= R_{\text{net}} & - H_{\text{sens}} & + H_{\text{waterflux}}, \end{aligned}$$

where the soil heat flux G serves as the Neumann boundary condition for the energy conservation equation of the subsurface domain. It is defined as positive when heat is conducted from the surface into the soil. The individual components are defined as follows. The net radiation R_{net} represents the total energy available from incoming and outgoing radiation, it is defined as positive when heat enters the surface. The sensible heat flux H_{sens} represents the heat transferred to the atmosphere through convection and conduction, it is defined as positive when heat leaves the surface. The water flux $H_{\text{waterflux}}$ accounts for the enthalpy exchange from precipitation and evapotranspiration, it is defined as positive when heat is added to the surface. This term implicitly incorporates the latent heat flux through the use of temperature-dependent enthalpies. Each term has units of energy flux per unit area [$\text{J}/\text{m}^2\text{s}$]. The resulting partitioning of energy at the soil-atmosphere interface is illustrated in Figure 3.1.

This heat balance only considers vertical fluxes, neglecting the horizontal transfer of energy through advection. Additional energy contributions, such as heat stored in vegetation, are assumed to be negligible compared to the primary terms.

Allen et al. explicitly include a latent heat flux to account for the energy required for evapotranspiration. In contrast, this work does not separate latent heat explicitly. Instead, the thermal effects of phase change are implicitly captured through the water heat flux term, which represents the enthalpy exchange of water entering as

Figure 3.1: Schematic of the surface energy balance at the soil-atmosphere interface (adapted from [32]). The net radiation R_{net} and the water heat flux $H_{\text{waterflux}}$ provide the primary energy inputs, while the sensible heat flux H_{sens} represents convective exchange with the atmosphere. The resulting residual G constitutes the Neumann boundary condition for the subsurface domain, representing the heat flux conducted into the soil matrix.

precipitation and leaving as vapor through evapotranspiration. By using temperature-dependent enthalpies of liquid and vapor water, this term inherently includes the latent heat. Since evapotranspiration is already resolved in the mass balance and coupled to the energy transport through these enthalpy-based fluxes, including a separate latent heat term would lead to a double-counted contribution.

The net radiation at the surface [24] is calculated as

$$R_{\text{net}} = H_{\text{short,in}}(1 - \omega) + H_{\text{long,in}} - \sigma T_{\text{abs}}^4, \quad (3.25)$$

with the incoming shortwave radiation $H_{\text{short,in}}$, the albedo ω which determines how much radiation is reflected at the surface, the incoming longwave radiation $H_{\text{long,in}}$, and the outgoing longwave radiation σT_{abs}^4 with the Stefan-Boltzmann constant σ and the absolute surface temperature in Kelvin T_{abs} . All parts in the sum have $[\text{J}/\text{m}^2\text{s}]$ as a unit.

The sensible heat flux H_{sens} [33] is defined as

$$H_{\text{sens}} = \frac{\rho_a c_p}{r_a} \cdot (T_{\text{surf}} - T_a), \quad (3.26)$$

where ρ_a is the mean air density [kg/m^3], c_p is the specific heat of air [J/kgK], r_a is the aerodynamic resistance [s/m], T_{surf} is the temperature at the ground surface [K], and T_a is the air temperature at a height of 2m [K].

The aerodynamic resistance r_a [s/m] governing the transfer of heat and water vapor from the evaporating surface into the air above the canopy [2] is given as

$$r_a = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{z_m-d}{z_{om}}\right) \ln\left(\frac{z_h-d}{z_{oh}}\right)}{k^2 u_z}, \quad (3.27)$$

where z_m is the height of wind measurements [m], z_h is the height of humidity measurements [m], d is the zero-plane displacement height [m], z_{om} is the roughness length governing momentum transfer [m], z_{oh} is the roughness length governing transfer of heat and vapor [m], k is Karman's constant, typically 0.41 [$-$], and u_z is the wind speed at height z [m/s].

The water heat flux is computed as

$$H_{\text{waterflux}} = (P \cdot h_{\text{precip}} - ET \cdot h_{\text{evap}}) \cdot M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}, \quad (3.28)$$

where P is the precipitation rate [$\text{mol}/\text{m}^2\text{s}$], ET is the evapotranspiration rate of water [$\text{mol}/\text{m}^2\text{s}$] which will be derived in the following part, h_{precip} and h_{evap} are the specific enthalpies of liquid and vapor water [J/kg], respectively, and $M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the molar mass of water [kg/mol].

3.3.2 Mass Flux Boundary Condition

In this section, we derive the expressions for mole fluxes at the ground-atmosphere interface. These fluxes are applied as Neumann conditions in the component mass conservation equations and represent the vertical mass exchange.

The total mass exchange is split into two main contributions, namely evapotranspiration and precipitation, which govern the liquid phase boundary flux, and gas-phase transport, which is modeled based on pressure differences between the domain and the atmosphere.

H₂O Mass Fluxes We begin by deriving the mole flux of each gaseous component due to evapotranspiration. The term of evapotranspiration is used to describe the combined process of evaporation from the soil and transpiration from vegetation.

The psychrometric constant γ [Pa/K] relates the partial pressure of water in air to the air temperature. Rewriting its definition for the specific heat of air c_p gives:

$$\gamma = \frac{c_p p_{\text{atm}}}{\varepsilon \lambda} \Leftrightarrow c_p = \gamma \cdot \frac{\varepsilon \lambda}{p_{\text{atm}}}, \quad (3.29)$$

where p_{atm} is the atmospheric pressure [Pa], ε is the ratio of the molecular weight of vapor to dry air with $\varepsilon = 0.622$, and λ is the latent heat of vaporization [J/kg].

Substituting this into the sensible heat flux expression (see Equation (3.26)) and splitting it into a temperature-independent factor h_{sens} leads to

$$H_{\text{sens}} = \frac{\rho_a \gamma \varepsilon \lambda}{r_a p_{\text{atm}}} \cdot (T_{\text{surf}} - T_a) = h_{\text{sens}} \cdot (T_{\text{surf}} - T_a) \quad (3.30)$$

$$\Rightarrow h_{\text{sens}} = \frac{\rho_a \gamma \varepsilon \lambda}{r_a p_{\text{atm}}}. \quad (3.31)$$

Analogously, we split the latent heat flux into a vapor pressure-independent part h_{ET} :

$$H_{ET} = h_{ET} \cdot (e_{\text{surf}} - e_a), \quad (3.32)$$

where e_{surf} and e_a are the vapor pressure at the surface and at 2m height, respectively [Pa]. The latent heat flux refers to the amount of energy absorbed or released during a phase change without a change in temperature.

Combining these two fluxes with the Bowen ratio:

$$\frac{H_{\text{sens}}}{H_{ET}} = \gamma \cdot \frac{T_{\text{surf}} - T_a}{e_{\text{surf}} - e_a}, \quad (3.33)$$

yields:

$$\gamma \cdot \frac{T_{\text{surf}} - T_a}{e_{\text{surf}} - e_a} = \frac{H_{\text{sens}}}{H_{ET}} = \frac{h_{\text{sens}} \cdot (T_{\text{surf}} - T_a)}{h_{ET} \cdot (e_{\text{surf}} - e_a)} \quad (3.34)$$

$$\Rightarrow h_{ET} = \frac{h_{\text{sens}}}{\gamma} = \frac{\rho_a \varepsilon \lambda}{r_a p_{\text{atm}}}. \quad (3.35)$$

This gives a final expression for the latent heat flux:

$$H_{ET} = \frac{\rho_a \varepsilon \lambda}{r_a p_{\text{atm}}} \cdot (e_{\text{surf}} - e_a). \quad (3.36)$$

Using the relation $H_{ET} = \lambda \cdot ET$ and thus dividing the previous equation by the latent heat of vaporization λ , the rate of evapotranspiration ET [$\text{mol}/\text{m}^2\text{s}$] is:

$$ET = \frac{\rho_a \varepsilon}{r_a p_{\text{atm}}} \cdot (e_{\text{surf}} - e_a). \quad (3.37)$$

Using the ideal gas law and expressing the vapor pressures as partial pressures $e_i = p_{\text{atm}} \cdot x_i$, we rewrite this as:

$$ET = \frac{\rho_a \varepsilon}{r_a} \cdot (x_{\text{surf}} - x_a), \quad (3.38)$$

where x_{surf} and x_a are the component mole fractions in the gas phase at the surface and at 2m, respectively [-].

This evapotranspiration rate is combined with the precipitation rate P to give the total liquid-phase molar flux $j^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$:

$$j^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = -P + ET. \quad (3.39)$$

Air Mass Flux In addition to evapotranspiration, we account for advective fluxes of gas phase components across the top boundary. These are driven by pressure differences between the gas phase in the domain and the atmospheric pressure.

If the gas pressure at the top boundary exceeds the atmospheric pressure, gas flux occurs from the domain into the atmosphere, otherwise inward flow occurs. This advective gas exchange is described by a pressure-driven flux, derived from Darcy's law, and formulated as:

$$j_n^\kappa = \frac{p_n - p_{\text{atm}}}{\delta z} \cdot \lambda_n \cdot K \cdot \rho_n^{\text{mol}} \cdot x_n^\kappa, \quad (3.40)$$

where j_n^κ is the advective mole flux of component κ , p_n is the gas pressure in the top-most cell, p_{atm} is the atmospheric pressure, δz is the distance from the cell center to the boundary face, λ_n denotes the gas phase mobility, K is the intrinsic permeability of the porous medium, ρ_n^{mol} is the molar density of the gas phase, and x_n^κ is the mole fraction of component κ in the gas phase.

To ensure consistency with physical boundary conditions, the composition of inflowing gas is assumed to match atmospheric values. In contrast, for outflow, the gas composition is taken directly from the simulation domain, representing the internal state of the system.

Summary of Boundary Conditions The boundary conditions defined at the top surface couple the porous medium to atmospheric influences and serve as essential closure relations for the conservation laws.

The Neumann boundary condition for energy introduces the heat balance at the ground surface into the energy conservation equation, with contributions from net radiation, sensible heat, and water-related enthalpy fluxes.

Simultaneously, the Neumann boundary conditions for component transport reflect mass exchange due to evapotranspiration and pressure-driven gas flow, entering the mole balance equations for each component.

Together these surface fluxes ensure that the simulation domain interacts realistically with its environment and enables the consistent resolution of coupled heat and mass transport across the ground-atmosphere interface.

4 Numerical Implementation

This chapter describes the numerical implementation of the coupled non-isothermal two-phase multi-component evapotranspiration model. The model is implemented in the open-source porous-media simulator DuMu^x (release 3.8) [14, 18], which is based on the Distributed and Unified Numerics Environment Dune (DUNE) [5, 4].

The simulation utilizes a custom 2pNcNI model (Two-Phase, N -Component, Non-Isothermal) implemented within the DuMu^x framework. This formulation extends the standard non-isothermal 2p2c (Two-Phase, Two-Component) model to allow the simulation of $N = 3$ distinct components examined in this work, namely CO₂, H₂O, and Air. The resulting system of governing equations is solved in time using a fully implicit Euler scheme. For spatial discretization, the Box method [18], a control volume finite element method, is used to enforce a degree of freedom at the interface. It unites the mass-conservative properties of finite volume methods with the ability of finite element methods to handle unstructured grids.

4.1 Code Structure and Coupling Concept

The implementation follows the modular DuMu^x framework. The specific extensions developed for this work are organized as follows, with the most important classes and methods visualized in Figure 4.1:

- `main.cc`: The simulation driver, which controls the time loop, the Newton solver, and the VTK output.
- `properties.hh`: Defines the type tag, fluid system (`FluidSystems::H2OAirCO2`), and grid type.
- `problem.hh`: Contains the `EvaporationProblem` class, which defines the initial conditions and the boundary conditions.
- `spatialparams.hh`: Defines the spatially varying constitutive relations, specifically the `EvaporationSpatialParams` class, which handles porosity, permeability, and the Van Genuchten-Mualem relationships.
- `surfaceflux.hh` and `weatherdataparser.hh`: These classes handle the coupling to the atmosphere. The parser reads meteorological data, while the surface flux class calculates the exchange fluxes based on the current solution state.

Figure 4.1: Diagram of relevant classes.

Conceptually, the model consists of a soil column solved by DuMu^x, coupled to a dataset of atmospheric forcing. At each time step, the Neumann boundary routine queries the **SurfaceFlux** module. This module uses the current soil surface state (pressure, temperature) and the current weather data to compute the precise mass and energy fluxes entering or leaving the domain.

The coupling mechanism is iterative and occurs within the DuMu^x Newton solver loop, as visualized in Figure 4.2. At each iteration, the current iterative state of the soil surface is passed to the **EvaporationProblem** boundary routine. This routine triggers the **SurfaceFlux** module, which retrieves the necessary atmospheric forcing via the **WeatherDataParser** to compute the mass and energy fluxes. These fluxes are

Figure 4.2: Flowchart of the coupling algorithm and time-stepping procedure.

then returned to the solver to update the residuals of the conservation equations until convergence is achieved.

4.2 Domain Setup and Grid Generation

The computational domain represents a 2D cross-section of the soil column. The grid is structured and implemented using a `Dune::YaspGrid`. Geometry and resolution are defined in the input file (`params.input`). To resolve steep gradients in saturation and temperature at the soil-atmosphere interface, grid grading is applied. Cell sizes decrease toward the upper boundary of the domain, ensuring high resolution where coupling fluxes are applied.

4.3 Spatial Parameters and Constitutive Relations

The hydraulic and thermal properties of the soil are represented and parameterized in the `EvaporationSpatialParams` class. The porous medium is characterized by the

following:

- **Hydraulic Properties:** The fluid-matrix interaction is described by the Van Genuchten-Mualem model. Key parameters such as α , n , and residual saturations (S_{wr} , S_{nr}) are read from the parameter tree.
- **Permeability:** The intrinsic permeability is derived using the Kozeny-Carman relationship, scaling with porosity.
- **Thermal Properties:** The solid soil matrix is assigned a specific heat capacity (C_s), density (ρ_s), and thermal conductivity (λ_s).

4.4 Boundary Conditions

The core of this research implementation is the handling of the top boundary condition in the `EvaporationProblem` class. A schematic of the computational domain and the distribution of these boundary conditions is illustrated in Figure 4.3. All boundaries are set to Neumann flux conditions, with the lateral and bottom boundaries treated as no-flow boundaries for both mass and heat, representing an isolated soil column.

The choice of a no-flow condition at the bottom boundary is physically motivated by the specific characteristics of karst systems with thin soil cover. In such environments, the limited overburden prevents the assumption of a constant water reservoir, which is often modeled using constant saturation Dirichlet conditions in deeper soil studies. Because the thin soil matrix is underlain by fractured rock, water is not replenished from below, rather the system’s total mass is governed by surface infiltration and evapotranspiration. The Neumann no-flow boundary thus fixes the total water mass within the system, allowing the model to accurately reflect the depletion of the limited capillary buffer.

The boundary fluxes are provided by overriding the `neumann()` method, which returns the component-wise mass fluxes and the energy flux for a given boundary control volume. At the top surface, the Neumann condition couples the subsurface domain with the atmosphere by imposing fluxes for the mass conservation equations (H₂O and Air components) and the energy conservation equation. It is based on the physical formulations developed in Section 3.3.

The H₂O mass balance is implemented according to Equation (3.39). The flux of the water component $j^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ imposes the net exchange of the water mass by combining liquid precipitation and gaseous evapotranspiration.

The Air mass balance is implemented according to Equation (3.40). To ensure numerical stability and physical consistency, an upwinding scheme is used for the mole fraction x_n^{Air} :

Figure 4.3: Schematic of the 2D computational domain and boundary conditions. The top boundary is governed by the surface energy balance, where the soil heat flux G acts as the residual Neumann boundary condition. Lateral and bottom boundaries are set to Neumann no-flow conditions to represent a system with limited water storage, typical of thin soil overburden in karst environments. The internal grid illustrates the grading used.

- Outflow ($p_n > p_{\text{atm}}$): Air leaving the domain carries the properties of the soil gas.
- Inflow ($p_n < p_{\text{atm}}$): Air entering the domain carries the properties of the atmosphere.

This implements a permeable boundary for the gas phase that allows air to be displaced by heat or water, or to be sucked in during cooling or drainage.

The energy flux is computed by the `SurfaceFlux` class. It accounts for net radiation, sensible heat flux, and the enthalpy transport associated with the mass fluxes.

Atmospheric forcing data are taken from the hydrometeorological dataset provided by Nissler and Haslauer [26] and stored locally as `measure_data.csv`, which contains daily measurements for radiation, temperature, humidity, precipitation, and wind speed. To

evaluate these boundary conditions at any given simulation time step, the custom `WeatherDataParser` class reads this file. It maps the continuous simulation time to the closest available daily weather record using a binary search algorithm, ensuring efficient and robust temporal matching throughout the simulation run.

To ensure that the numerical implementation matches the physical theory, several specific parameterizations are used:

- Latent heat of vaporization λ :

The latent heat of vaporization is used to transfer equations from kinematic units to energetic units. It is often approximated to be a constant value of 2.45 MJ [2], but in this work the temperature-dependent empirical formula of [15, p. 52] is used:

$$\lambda = 2500827 - 2360(T - 273.15) \quad [\text{J/kg}]. \quad (4.1)$$

- Air density and virtual temperature:

The sensible heat flux calculation (3.26) contains the air density ρ_a which is calculated via the ideal gas law:

$$\rho_a = \frac{P}{T_{Kv}R}, \quad (4.2)$$

where $T_{Kv} = 1.01(T + 273)$ [K] is the virtual temperature that accounts for humidity and R [J/kgK] is the specific gas constant for dry air.

Finally, it is important to note a critical distinction between the sign convention used in the mathematical formulation of the surface energy balance and its numerical implementation within the DuMu^x framework. In Chapter 3, the soil heat flux G (3.24) is defined from the perspective of the soil, where a positive value indicates energy *entering* the subsurface. However, DuMu^x utilizes a standard numerical convention for Neumann boundary conditions based on the unit outward normal vector \mathbf{n} . In this convention, the flux is defined as positive when it is in the direction of the normal, meaning it is *leaving* the domain. To ensure consistency with the solver's requirements, the signs of the individual flux components are inverted within the implementation of the boundary condition evaluation.

4.5 Initial Conditions

Initial conditions are set in `EvaporationProblem::initialAtPos`. The pressure is initialized hydrostatically:

$$p(z) = p_{\text{init}} - \rho g z. \quad (4.3)$$

The temperature and gas saturation are initialized to constant values, which are defined in the `params.input` file.

4.6 Output and Diagnostics

The simulation generates standard VTK output for visualization (e.g., in ParaView [1]). Additionally, a specific logging mechanism was implemented to track surface exchange processes. The `SurfaceFlux` class writes a `surface_flux_log.csv` file at every time step, recording instantaneous values for precipitation, net radiation, latent heat flux, sensible heat flux, and surface temperature. This allows for a detailed post-processing and validation of the coupling algorithm.

5 Simulation Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the implemented non-isothermal, two-phase, three-component evapo-transpiration model is evaluated. While the model is multicomponent, the following analysis focuses on the partitioning of energy and water mass fluxes, as these represent the primary drivers for any subsequent gas transport study. First, the experimental setup and the environmental boundary conditions are introduced. Subsequently, the evolution of the implementation of the numerical boundary condition is discussed, highlighting the coupling between numerical stability, spatial discretization, and physical realism.

5.1 Experimental Setup

To validate the surface flux formulations, a one dimensional soil column is modeled using the porous medium properties of sand. The primary objective is to observe the dynamic partitioning of energy and mass fluxes across the top boundary driven by atmospheric forcing and the numerical stability and physical realism of the coupled surface flux formulations.

To focus on surface flux partitioning, CO_2 is treated as a passive component in the following simulations. It is initialized with a zero mole fraction throughout the domain and is not subject to any internal source terms or atmospheric inflow. This allows for a targeted evaluation of the coupled water and heat transfer mechanisms without CO_2 concentration gradients influencing the phase behavior or numerical stability.

The atmospheric driving forces are provided by a measured meteorological dataset for Stuttgart [26]. The dataset contains daily averages and accumulations for shortwave radiation ($H_{\text{short,in}}$), incoming longwave radiation ($H_{\text{long,in}}$), air temperature at a height of 2 m (T_a), relative humidity (RH), precipitation (P), and wind speed at a height of 2 m (u). The values for the first three simulation days, which serve as the primary evaluation period for the transient flux analysis, are summarized in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: Daily meteorological forcing data for the first three simulation days.

Date	$H_{\text{short,in}}$ [W/m^2]	$H_{\text{long,in}}$ [W/m^2]	T_a [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	RH [%]	P [mm]	u [m/s]
2019-08-08	253.88	343.38	19.08	79.51	0.002	0.48
2019-08-09	220.69	381.86	22.48	75.07	0.114	0.36
2019-08-10	217.18	371.82	20.65	75.95	0.180	0.44

Two distinct spatial domains are investigated to evaluate the influence of the capillary buffer on the evapotranspiration regime: a shallow 2 cm domain, representing a small-scale laboratory sample, and a deeper 20 cm domain, representing a more realistic field-scale soil profile. In both cases, the initial gas saturation is set to $S_n = 0.5$, the initial temperature is set to $T = 299$ K, and the irreducible water saturation is defined as $S_{wr} = 0.25$. A summary of the primary properties of the porous medium and initial boundary conditions utilized in the numerical model is provided in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2: Macroscopic porous medium properties and initial simulation conditions representing a sandy soil column.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Initial porosity	ϕ	0.4	–
Initial permeability	K	1×10^{-13}	m^2
Van Genuchten parameter	α	1.5×10^{-4}	Pa^{-1}
Van Genuchten parameter	n	14.0	–
Irreducible liquid saturation	S_{wr}	0.25	–
Irreducible gas saturation	S_{gr}	0.025	–
Solid density	ρ_s	2650	kg/m^3
Solid heat capacity	c_s	850	$\text{J}/(\text{kg} \cdot \text{K})$
Solid thermal conductivity	λ_s	2.5	$\text{W}/(\text{m} \cdot \text{K})$
Initial CO ₂ mole fraction	$x_{w,\text{init}}^{\text{CO}_2}$	0.0	–
Initial pressure	p_{init}	1.0×10^5	Pa
Initial temperature	T_{init}	299	K
Initial gas saturation	$S_{n,\text{init}}$	0.5	–
Boundary layer thickness	d_{bl}	1.0	cm

5.2 Evolution of Atmospheric Forcing Interpolation

A fundamental challenge in environmental modeling is the discrepancy in temporal resolution between available meteorological data, often recorded as daily averages, and the continuous nature of the partial differential equations solved by the numerical model. The method chosen to map discrete daily data onto the continuous simulation time drastically affects both the stability of the Newton solver and the physical validity of the calculated fluxes. To demonstrate this, three different atmospheric forcing interpolation schemes are implemented and evaluated. The resulting atmospheric forcing for these three methods is visualized in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Comparison of the three different weather data interpolation methods: Nearest Neighbor (left), Linear Interpolation (center), and Diurnal Cycles (right).

5.2.1 Direct Data Application

The most naive approach to handling daily atmospheric data is a direct nearest-neighbor assignment, where the weather variables for a given simulation time t are assigned the values of the closest recorded day. As seen in Figure 5.1 (left), this approach is mathematically faithful to the raw input data but creates C^0 discontinuities at midnight.

5.2.2 Linear Interpolation

To mitigate the discrete step functions, a continuous linear interpolation scheme is implemented. Daily averages are assigned to noon on their respective days, and values for any intermediate time t are calculated using linear interpolation between adjacent days. As shown in Figure 5.1 (center), this successfully smooths the meteorological forcing. However, by linearly interpolating shortwave solar radiation ($H_{\text{short,in}}$) across 24 hours, the model effectively simulates a continuous mild solar forcing that persists even during the night, while severely underestimating the midday peak.

5.2.3 Overlaying Diurnal Cycles

To reconcile numerical stability with physical realism, a synthetic diurnal cycle is superimposed onto the linearly interpolated daily averages (Figure 5.1, right). Using standard micro-meteorological approximations, the shortwave radiation is restricted to a 12-hour daylight period using a sine wave, scaled so that the total integral of the curve conserves the daily average provided by the weather dataset. These approximations fundamentally assume that incoming shortwave radiation follows a sinus-like half-wave between sunrise and sunset. A similar continuous sine wave is applied to the air temperature, shifting the peak to the early afternoon to mimic realistic atmospheric heating. Note that precipitation is intentionally kept as a continuous linear interpolation without a diurnal overlay, as linearly smearing rain accumulations is a standard simplification that avoids the severe numerical shocks associated with discrete precipitation step-functions.

5.3 Resulting Surface Fluxes and Thermal Response

To isolate the effects of the three atmospheric forcing schemes and evaluate their physical validity, the following results are extracted from simulations utilizing the 20 cm spatial domain. This ensures that the soil column has a sufficient capillary buffer to sustain evapotranspiration without premature numerical failure.

5.3.1 Energy Partitioning

The partitioning of the available energy at the soil surface into net radiation, sensible heat, water heat, and soil heat fluxes is the primary driver of the system's thermodynamics. Figure 5.2 illustrates the profound impact of the chosen interpolation scheme on this energy balance.

The nearest-neighbor approach produces highly unrealistic step-responses. The net radiation (R_{net}) jumps instantaneously, forcing the sensible heat and soil heat fluxes to spike at midnight. The numerical shocks are particularly violent for the soil heat flux (G), which exhibits nonphysical instantaneous gradients exceeding 300 W/m^2 , before decaying exponentially as the soil matrix slowly acclimates to the sudden boundary change.

Linear interpolation resolves these shocks, providing smooth, numerically stable curves. However, the physical representation is highly flawed because $H_{\text{short,in}}$ is smeared over 24 hours, R_{net} remains positive throughout the entire night, completely failing to capture nocturnal thermal dynamics.

The diurnal cycle model successfully recovers the physical reality of the surface energy balance. During the day, the sine-wave-driven shortwave radiation creates massive positive R_{net} peaks. At night, $H_{\text{short,in}}$ drops to zero, but the soil continues to emit

Figure 5.2: Comparison of the resulting energy fluxes of the three interpolation methods at the soil surface.

longwave thermal radiation. This causes R_{net} to drop below zero, representing nocturnal radiative cooling. Consequently, the sensible heat flux (H_{sens}) and the soil heat flux (G) show clear day-night sign reversals: during the day, the hot surface heats the air and conducts heat into the deeper soil (positive fluxes), while at night, the radiatively cooled surface extracts heat from both the atmosphere and the deeper soil layer (negative fluxes). The water heat flux ($H_{\text{waterflux}}$), which represents the energy advected by evaporating water or infiltrating precipitation, remains comparatively small in magnitude but dynamically follows the diurnal cycle, carrying latent heat out of the system during peak midday evapotranspiration.

5.3.2 Mass Exchange

Evapotranspiration in porous media is primarily driven by the vapor pressure deficit and the available energy at the surface. The dynamic response of the mass fluxes is shown in Figure 5.3. While the model solves for the transport of three components (H_2O , Air, and CO_2), only the H_2O mass flux is shown in the figure. The CO_2 flux remains zero as a result of the initialization, and the Air mass flux, while calculated

via pressure-driven advection, is secondary to the evapotranspiration-driven water exchange in the current analysis.

Figure 5.3: Comparison of the resulting mass fluxes (evapotranspiration and precipitation) for the three interpolation methods.

Using the nearest-neighbor scheme, the mass fluxes exhibit the same nonphysical step-responses seen in the energy balance. The evapotranspiration rate spikes instantaneously at midnight when the new daily average variables are applied, completely decoupling the mass exchange from the actual daytime solar forcing.

The linear interpolation model yields a gentle continuous evapotranspiration rate that spans the entire 24-hour period. Because the saturated vapor pressure of water depends exponentially on temperature, this linear method severely underestimates the true magnitude of the evaporative demand during the hottest parts of the day.

Conversely, the diurnal cycle model captures the highly non-linear nature of evapotranspiration. The evapotranspiration rate (ET) spikes aggressively during the early afternoon, perfectly in phase with the net radiation and temperature peaks, reaching magnitudes nearly triple those of the linear model ($\approx 0.007 \text{ mol}/(\text{m}^2\text{s})$). At night, as the surface cools and the available radiant energy disappears, the vapor pressure gradient shrinks, correctly shutting down the evapotranspiration process to near zero.

5.3.3 Thermal Response

The resulting surface temperature (T_{surf}) is not a prescribed boundary condition, but is calculated implicitly by the Newton solver to satisfy the conservation of energy.

Figure 5.4 compares the thermal response to the background air temperature (T_a).

Figure 5.4: Comparison of the atmospheric driving temperature (T_a) and the resulting simulated surface temperature (T_{surf}).

Under the nearest-neighbor approach, the thermal response is completely dominated by the nonphysical step-changes at midnight. For example, a sharp temperature spike occurs on day 0.5, which coincides visibly with the onset of the first precipitation event. However, this is not a physical thermodynamic reaction to the rainfall. Because the parser updates all weather variables in the exact same millisecond, the start of the precipitation coincides perfectly with a massive jump in the air temperature boundary condition (T_a) from day 0 (19.08 °C) to day 1 (22.48 °C). The surface temperature increases immediately by approximately 3.4 °C to match this new atmospheric forcing. In contrast, on day 1.5, the model is lowered from day 1 to day 2 (20.65 °C), causing an immediate drop in T_{surf} . Thus, the surface merely reacts to the discontinuous shocks in the air temperature boundary condition, rather than modeling the physical evaporative cooling or sensible heat transfer of the water itself.

While the linear model shows a slow featureless drift in T_{surf} , the diurnal model exhibits realistic thermal inertia and extreme dynamics. During intense midday heating, T_{surf} increases steeply, reaching a peak significantly higher than the ambient air temperature (reaching up to approximately 35 °C). Crucially, during the night, the nocturnal radiative cooling causes the surface to lose energy rapidly. As a result, T_{surf} dips correctly below the background air temperature T_a , accurately reflecting the complex thermodynamic coupling between the soil and the atmosphere.

5.4 Influence of the Spatial Domain Depth

The progression of atmospheric forcing schemes from discrete steps to continuous diurnal cycles reveals a critical dependency between physically accurate boundary conditions and spatial discretization of the domain.

To explicitly isolate the effect of the domain depth without triggering immediate numerical failure, the linear interpolation scheme is used to compare the 2 cm and 20 cm

soil columns. The resulting energy fluxes, mass fluxes, and surface temperatures are shown in Figure 5.6, Figure 5.5, and Figure 5.7.

Figure 5.5: Comparison of the resulting mass fluxes for the 2 cm and 20 cm domains under linear interpolation.

As seen in the mass exchange comparison (Figure 5.5), the shallow 2 cm domain exhibits signs of hydraulic limitation. The evapotranspiration rate (ET) decays more noticeably during the first two days compared to the 20 cm domain, because the limited capillary water buffer in the shallow soil is depleted. This rapid drying is an artifact of the Neumann no-flow boundary condition, while a constant saturation at the bottom would act as an infinite water reservoir to prevent drying, such a setup would be physically unrealistic for thin karst overburdens. In contrast, the 20 cm domain maintains higher and more stable evapotranspiration rates by drawing water upward from deeper layers. This restricted evapotranspiration in the shallow domain directly impacts energy partitioning (Figure 5.6) and the thermal response (Figure 5.7). With less latent heat being removed from the system via the water heat flux, the surface of the 2 cm domain becomes slightly warmer, peaking higher than that of the 20 cm domain. To maintain the surface energy balance, this excess heat must be dissipated through a higher sensible heat flux.

Figure 5.6: Comparison of the resulting surface energy fluxes for the 2 cm and 20 cm domains under linear interpolation.

Figure 5.7: Comparison of the resulting surface temperatures for the 2 cm and 20 cm domains under linear interpolation.

These comparisons demonstrate that even under mild and continuous forcing, a shallow domain alters the physical balance of the system. Although the shallow domain is capable of converging under the nearest neighbor and linear interpolation schemes, the introduction of intense, physically accurate midday solar radiation via the diurnal cycles exposes a severe limitation. During peak daytime heating ($H_{\text{short,in}} > 600 \text{ W/m}^2$), the massive evaporative demand documented in Figure 5.3 rapidly depletes the limited volume of mobile water in the uppermost computational cells of the 2 cm domain. Within hours, the saturation drops to the irreducible water saturation ($S_{wr} = 0.25$). At this limit, the liquid phase becomes perfectly immobile, causing capillary pressures to increase toward infinity. Because the diurnal atmospheric boundary condition continues to demand high latent heat fluxes while the cell lacks extractable water, the Newton solver encounters an unsolvable mathematical gradient and fails to converge.

This convergence failure is not merely a numerical problem, it highlights that the governing equations effectively degenerate when the model is applied to extremely thin overburdens that lack a hydraulic buffer. This establishes that simulating realistic high-frequency surface exchange requires a domain deep enough to provide realistic hydraulic buffering. The extended 20 cm domain acts as this necessary capillary buffer, allowing the strong midday evaporative demand at the surface to draw water upward from deeper layers, preventing instantaneous drying out and ensuring robust physically valid solver performance throughout the diurnal cycle. The successful resolution of these intense diurnal interactions confirms that the model's coupling of energy, water, and air mass balances is numerically robust, providing a validated framework into which CO_2 transport can be directly integrated in future studies.

6 Summary and Outlook

6.1 Summary and Conclusions

This work presented the development and implementation of a non-isothermal, two-phase, three-component numerical model designed to simulate coupled heat and mass transport in porous media. Motivated by conservation challenges in prehistoric sites such as the Lascaux cave, the model establishes a physically consistent framework to quantify the exchange of energy, water vapor, and CO₂ between the atmosphere and the subsurface.

The mathematical foundation utilizes Darcy-scale mass and momentum balances coupled with a single energy conservation equation, assuming local thermal equilibrium between the fluid phases and the solid matrix. By employing the DuMu^x simulation framework, the model successfully integrates atmospheric forcing data to drive surface energy fluxes of net radiation, sensible heat, and water heat, as well as mass fluxes of H₂O and Air. A primary achievement was the derivation of a boundary condition equation system based on the Penman-Monteith framework and the Bowen ratio. This system accurately describes the physical dependencies at the interface, ensuring that surface fluxes remain consistent with both atmospheric demand and the internal state of the soil.

A central focus of the analysis was the role of evapotranspiration, which acts as the critical link between mass and energy balances. The simulations revealed that it is not merely a loss of water mass but a dominant cooling mechanism via latent heat transfer. During peak midday heating, the evapotranspiration rate reaches magnitudes nearly triple those estimated by simplified linear models, highlighting its nonlinear dependence on temperature and vapor gradients.

Furthermore, the simulation analysis emphasized the critical role of the temporal resolution of the meteorological data. Although direct data application or linear interpolation of daily averages may be sufficient for long-term climate studies where cumulative totals are the primary interest, they are inadequate for short time window inspections. Such simplifications do not capture essential nocturnal radiative cooling and midday evaporative peaks that drive the transient behavior of the system. The implementation of a synthetic diurnal cycle proved superior by accurately recovering day-night sign reversals in soil heat flux and providing a realistic hydraulic response. Finally, the study demonstrated that sufficient spatial domain depth, acting as capillary buffer, is

required to maintain realistic high-frequency evaporation rates without causing numerical failure due to instantaneous soil drying.

6.2 Outlook

Although the current framework provides a robust basis for modeling soil-atmosphere interactions, several directions for future research are identified to enhance its predictive capability.

Although CO₂ was treated as a passive component in this initial evaluation, the model is fully equipped to simulate active CO₂ transport. Future studies should incorporate internal source terms, such as soil respiration, to investigate how atmospheric fluctuations drive gas exchange into subterranean cavities.

The present model incorporates atmospheric and cave influences through boundary conditions. Extending the implementation to include a fully coupled free-flow domain for the atmosphere and the internal cave air space would allow a more detailed representation of ventilation patterns and boundary layer resistances.

The current simulations used a homogeneous sandy soil profile. Incorporating more complex soil types, multi-layered geometries, and the effects of hydraulic hysteresis would improve the model's realism for site-specific conservation studies.

Future work should focus on validating the simulated surface fluxes and thermal responses against high-resolution field measurements or controlled laboratory experiments to further refine the constitutive relations and coupling coefficients.

Ultimately, this modeling framework serves as a prerequisite for the robust prediction of how sensitive subterranean microclimates respond to global environmental change. It provides a grounded scientific tool to support the long-term preservation of cultural heritage against the challenges of an evolving climate.

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